

CORROSION INHIBITION STUDY OF WAAM-CMT FABRICATED 316L STAINLESS STEEL IN 0.5 M SULFURIC ACID BY AN AMINOPHENOL-DERIVED SCHIFF BASE: ELECTROCHEMICAL AND SURFACE ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT: Wire arc addition (WAAM-CMT) technology enables faster and more cost-effective product design compared to other currently available additive manufacturing methods. This technology uses wire as the raw material and an electric arc as the heat source to build the metal components layer by layer. Known for its high deposition rates and cost-effectiveness, this technology is particularly well-suited for large-scale, complex structures. The final product exhibits a highly specialized, heterogeneous microstructure due to its thermal history. Currently, very few studies exist on the corrosion resistance of 316L steel when fabricated using the WAAM-CMT technique. Therefore, this study focuses specifically on the corrosion resistance of 316L steel fabricated using the WAAM-CMT technique in an acidic medium, specifically 0.5 M sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4), in the absence and presence of various concentrations from $5 \cdot 10^{-6}$ to 10^{-3} M of an aminophenol-derived Schiff base (SB) inhibitor, at constant immersion temperatures, using electrochemical methods, specifically electrodynamic polarization and spectroscopic impedance measurement. The samples were analyzed using scanning electron microscopy, which confirmed the adsorption of the inhibitor onto the contact surface between the steel and the solution. Therefore, this organic compound acts as a catalyst in the aggressive medium of 0.5 M sulfuric acid. The corrosion potential did not exhibit a consistent pattern with varying (SB) concentrations. The changing slope of the cathodic and anode Tafel curves highlights the mixed nature of the inhibitor. The addition of (SB) leads to a decrease in current density. The corrosion rate (i_{corr}) decreases with increasing ligand concentration, indicating that the inhibition process is due to the adsorption of (SB) onto the steel surface. The inhibition efficiency (EI%) shows an upward trend with increasing (SB) concentration. The optimal concentration of 10^{-3} M achieved an inhibition efficiency of 90.4%.

KEYWORDS: 316L stainless steel, Corrosion, Schiff base, Inhibitor, Additive manufacturing, CMT method.

1 INTRODUCTION

Additive manufacturing (AM) processes also known as 3D printing or direct digital manufacturing have been booming in recent years. They open up a world of possibilities for designing metal parts with complex geometries and multi-scale structural patterns (such as lattices or other structures) [1-2]. Compared to the capabilities of conventional, or subtractive, processes, these technologies offer gains in cost, mass, functional performance, and manufacturing efficiency. However, a lack of

knowledge about the properties and durability of the resulting parts currently limits their applications. Characterizing parts produced by additive manufacturing is therefore a key factor in the deployment of these technologies [3-4]

Consequently, a growing number of studies are being conducted to address the challenges associated with this production method, particularly the corrosion susceptibility of metals produced by (AM) [5]. Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) is an advanced fabrication technique that uses wire as feedstock and an electric arc as a heat source to build

metal components layer by layer. Known for its high deposition rates and cost-effectiveness, WAAM is particularly suited for large-scale, complex structures [6-7]. The WAAM process is a manufacturing technology that uses metal wire as a raw material and an electric arc as an energy source [8].

The wire is deposited at a predetermined speed and welded by the electric arc onto a substrate or a previous layer. WAAM has become competitive among manufacturing processes due to its high deposition rate (1-4 kg/h) [9], its lower environmental impact, productivity, and reduced costs and manufacturing times compared to other additive manufacturing processes [9]. However, this process is suitable for large parts and is not appropriate for small parts with high geometric complexity, such as powder bed processes. Thanks to its low buy-to-fly ratio [10]. The CMT process is a variant of the GMAW process, developed by Fronius to reduce energy consumption and heat buildup. This process differs from GMAW only in the method of separating the molten metal droplet by mechanical shrinkage which allows for a low heat input, thus mitigating the thermal gradient and residual stresses. This improves the mechanical behavior and dimensional accuracy of the generated parts [11-12]. The CMT process offers numerous advantages, notably its ability to operate synergistically. Synergy is a principle developed by Fronius that optimizes the generated electric arc. In this operating mode, the operator only needs to adjust the wire feed speed, while the voltage and current are automatically determined by the synergistic principle based on the selected speed. However, manual welding is also possible, if necessary. For these reasons, the research presented in this document is based on the CMT Standard process. A synergistic law adapted to the material studied was considered to improve weld quality. [13-14].

This study focuses on AISI 316L austenitic stainless steel, which is used in numerous sectors, including the chemical, pharmaceutical, petroleum, food processing, and maritime industries. Its resistance to marine and acidic environments, along with its high ductility, makes it a widely used material. This is why the production of 316L stainless steel by additive manufacturing is a real challenge. Additive-manufactured (WAAM -CMT) 316L stainless steel exhibits excellent resistance to corrosion compared to conventional 316L and fatigue strength comparable to the latter, but which remains highly dependent on printing conditions [15,16].

Corrosion of 316L in additive manufacturing is a key issue, as this type of stainless steel is widely used

for its excellent corrosion resistance properties and good suitability for 3D printing. However, the microstructure resulting from additive manufacturing processes differs from that of forged or rolled materials, which can influence its corrosion behavior [17,18]. In order to contribute to the various research relating on the one hand to the corrosion of steels and their inhibition in the various solutions encountered in the industrial sector. In our research, we investigated the inhibitory efficacy of a newly synthesized aminophenol-derived Schiff base (SB) inhibitor with a molar mass $M=243.25$ g/mol and chemical formula $C_{14}H_{13}NO_3$ [19], against the corrosion of 316L steel manufactured additively by the CMT method in 0.5M sulfuric acid environments. We employed electrochemical techniques, specifically potentiodynamic polarization and impedance spectroscopy, to assess the performance of this Schiff base as a corrosion inhibitor. Our findings contribute to the understanding of how this compound can effectively protect steel in aggressive acidic conditions.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

The working electrode used in our study is 316L steel manufactured additively the CMT method, which is primarily composed of iron, along with several alloying elements that enhance its mechanical and corrosion-resistant properties. Fig. 1 shows an image of samples used in this work.

Fig. 1 photo of used samples manufactured additively by CMT

The steel surface is initially stripped by mechanical polishing with abrasive paper of different grain sizes, then rinsed with distilled water. The electrode thus has a very smooth surface allowing reproducible results

2.1 Electrochemical investigations

The experimental setup used in this work is a VOLTALAB PGZ 301, allowing electrochemical measurements assisted by a microcomputer connected to an appropriate interface and equipped with voltamaster4 software for data acquisition and processing, as well as the determination of various electrochemical parameters. The electrochemical experiments were conducted in a thermostated cylindrical glass measuring cell with a capacity of 100 mL. This setup is equipped with a simple ground

cover featuring five holes, which allows for the precise positioning of our working electrodes in a fixed and reproducible manner.

The components of the electrodes are as follows:

Firstly: Working Electrode a cylindrical piece of 316L steel with a diameter of 6 mm.

Secondly: Reference Electrode: an Ag/AgCl reference electrode, which maintains a constant potential of 140 mV versus the normal hydrogen electrode (ENH).

In this study, we used a platinum counter electrode with a surface area of 1 cm². This counter electrode was strategically positioned near the working electrode to ensure a homogeneous electric field throughout the cell. The steel surface is initially stripped by mechanical polishing with abrasive paper of different grain sizes, then rinsed with distilled water. The electrode thus has a very smooth surface allowing reproducible results. After several tests and according to the literature [20-21]. The study of the inhibitory action of the ligand on the corrosion of steel after 30 min of immersion in 0.5 M H₂SO₄ medium by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in a range of 100 kHz to 10 mHz was demonstrated at room temperature. The plotting of the polarization curves was carried out in a potential range corresponding to (-800 mV to -200 mV) with respect to Ag /AgCl. we worked with a speed of 2mV/s.

2.2 Results and discussions

Our primary goal was to assess the inhibitory capacity of the (SB) in 0.5M (H₂SO₄) media, both with and without varying concentrations of the inhibitor from 5.10⁻⁶ to 10⁻³M. we used two methods: a stationary method (polarization curves) and the other transient (impedance spectroscopy).

2.2.1 Results of impedancemetry

All Nyquist plots (or electrochemical impedance spectra) are commonly used to analyze the electrochemical properties of materials and interfaces. When comparing these plots in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the (SB), we can observe changes in charge transfer resistance, double layer capacitance, and other electrochemical parameters. Fig. 2 depicts Nyquist diagrams obtained at 25°C for 316L steel immersed in 0.5M (H₂SO₄) media, both without and with varying concentrations of the (SB). According to the literatures [22,23]

In the absence of the (sb):

At low concentrations, the (sb) can modify the structure of the electric double layer and influence the charge transfer kinetics, thus altering the size and shape of the Nyquist arc.

Fig. 2 Nyquist diagrams for 316L steel in the absence and presence of different concentrations of the (SB) in 30 min of immersion H₂SO₄ 0.5 M at 25°C.

The diameters of the Nyquist diagrams in Fig. 2 are influenced by the concentration of the (SB). As the concentration of the (SB) increases, the impedance of the 316L steel electrode in the acidic media also increases. This indicates that the inhibitor molecules are covering more of the metal surface, leading to a higher rate of inhibition. Tables 1 summarize the electrochemical parameters derived from the impedance data, including polarization resistance (Rp), which is calculated from the impedance difference at low and high frequencies. From equation (1) the values of the double layer capacitance (Cdl) were obtained

$$f(-Z_{max}) = \frac{1}{2\pi C_{dl} R_p} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

From equation (2) we calculated the inhibition efficiency:

$$EI (\%) = \frac{R_{pinh} - R_p}{R_{pinh}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where Rp and Rpinh are the values of the polarization resistance in the absence and presence of the (SB). respectively.

Table 1. Electrochemical parameters of impedancemetry in the absence and presence of different concentrations of (sb) at 25°C.

C(M)	Rs(Ohm.cm2)	Rp (Ohm.cm2)	C _{dl} (μF.cm ²)	IE%
0	1.70	20.19	280.5	-
5.10 ⁻⁶	2.41	36.06	157.1	44
5.10 ⁻⁵	2.61	36.24	156.3	44.3
10 ⁻⁴	3.26	85.37	149.1	76.4
5.10 ⁻⁴	3.75	120.6	105.5	76.4
10 ⁻³	3.62	165.2	152.1	87.8

The results obtained in Table 1 revealed that the presence of the inhibitor leads to an increase in the polarization resistance value with increasing concentration and a decrease in the double layer capacitance (Cdl) as the amount of inhibitor

increases. The decrease in C_{dl} is due to the adsorption of the ligand onto the steel surface.

This observation suggests that the (SB) molecules are adsorbing onto the 316L steel surface, forming a stable protective layer. As the amount of adsorbed (SB) increases, the thickness of this protective layer grows, resulting in a decrease in the double layer capacitance. The inhibitory efficiency of this compound increases with the ligand concentration, reaching a maximum value of 87.8% at 10^{-3} M.

2.2.2 Results of Potentiodynamic polarization

Tafel curves allow the analysis of the electrochemical behavior of 316L stainless steel in an acidic solution such as 0.5M (H_2SO_4) and the evaluation of the effect of adding corrosion inhibitors, such as (SB). Fig. 3 presents the polarization curves of 316L steel in 0.5M (H_2SO_4) solutions, both before and after the addition of the (SB) at different concentrations

Fig. 3 Tafel curves without and with addition of different concentrations of (SB) after 30 min of immersion at 25°C

Without (SB): 316L steel in 0.5M (H_2SO_4) medium exhibits active corrosion with high corrosion current density (i_{corr}) values and a relatively low corrosion potential (E_{corr}).

With (SB): The addition of the inhibitor results in: a decrease in i_{corr} , indicating a reduction in the corrosion rate. a shift in the potential E_{corr} , which allows us to identify whether the inhibitor acts as an anodic, cathodic, or mixed inhibitor. A change in the anodic (β_a) and cathodic (β_c) slopes, revealing the inhibition mechanism.

From the Tafel lines shown in Fig. 3, we were able to determine various electrochemical characteristics. Table 2 present the corrosion current densities (i_{corr}), corrosion potential (E_{corr}), cathodic and anodic Tafel slopes (β_c and β_a), and inhibition efficiency (EI%) for different

concentrations of the Schiff base in both 0.5M (H_2SO_4) media. The inhibitory efficiency is defined as follows:

$$EI(\%) = \frac{i_{corr}^{\circ} - i_{corr\ inh}}{i_{corr}^{\circ}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where: i_{corr}° and $i_{corr\ inh}$ represent the values of current densities of 316l steel immersed in acidic media respectively without and with the addition of (SB)

Table 2. Electrochemical parameters of impedancemetry in the absence and presence of different concentrations of (sb) at 25°C.

C (M)	0	$5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	10^{-4}	$5 \cdot 10^{-4}$	10^{-3}
$-E_i=0$ (mV/Ag/AgCl)	492	489.1	493	486.4	465.1	449.7
i_{corr} (mA.cm ⁻²)	0.76	0.39	0.31	0.13	0.08	0.07
β_a (mV.Dec ⁻¹)	204	108.17	66.22	62.11	67.56	41.6
$-\beta_c$ (mV.Dec ⁻¹)	159.61	113.39	70.43	76.47	88.48	49.38
τ_{corr} (mm/an)	14.53	7.32	9.33	2.36	1.20	2.89
θ	-	0.488	0.587	0.835	0.90	0.904
EI(%)	-	48.8	58.7	83.5	90	90.4

The effect of corrosion inhibitor concentration is a very important parameter in the effectiveness of corrosion protection. Generally, as the inhibitor concentration increases, the effectiveness of corrosion protection increases, up to a certain optimal threshold. we found the optimal concentration equal to 10^{-3} M and which gives the inhibition efficiency of 90.4%.

Analysis of the results obtained clearly shows that molecules (SB) possess excellent corrosion-inhibiting properties against 316L stainless steel in 0.5M (H_2SO_4). This behavior is probably due to the strong adsorption of molecules (SB) onto the Additive-manufactured (WAAM - CMT) 316L stainless steel surface. The presence of methoxy groups is responsible for this strong adsorption, which induces excellent inhibition of carbon steel by the studied molecules. Adsorption occurs via the lone pairs of electrons on the oxygen and/or nitrogen of the imine

2.2.3 SEM Analysis

The surface morphology of 316L stainless steel manufactured by (WAAM – CMT) was studied after 24 hours of immersion in 0.5M (H_2SO_4), in the absence and presence of (SB), under optimal conditions using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The results are shown in Fig 4. Fig 4(a) shows the SEM image of the steel surface before immersion. The surface shows no noticeable defects, only traces of polishing, and appears smooth and

intact. Figure 3(b) shows the damaged surface after immersion in the corrosive acid solution. The 316L steel sample deteriorated significantly, and rust formation was evident. The steel surface is irregular, and the corrosion is severe and accompanied by pitting. With the addition of the optimal concentration of (SB), as shown in Figure 4(c), the 316L steel sample was adequately protected from corrosion by the adsorbed inhibitor molecules, and a less corrosive and smoother surface was clearly observed. Thus, a sufficient protective surface layer was formed. Therefore, it can be concluded that Schiff base has good corrosion inhibition capabilities on of 316L stainless steel manufactured by (WAAM – CMT).

Fig. 4 Micrographs (SEM) of the surface of 316L stainless steel manufactured by (WAAM – CMT) (a), after 24 h of immersion in 0.5M (H₂SO₄) alone (b) and with (SB) 10⁻³ M (c)

CONCLUSION

This work has made it possible to meet the objectives set concerning the inhibitor against corrosion of 316L steel manufactured additively in 0.5M (H₂SO₄) by (SB) adsorption. Based on the results obtained, we can draw the following conclusions:

- The corrosion rate decreases with increasing bond concentration.
- The addition of the bond shifts the corrosion potential values towards more positive values.
- The slopes of the cathode and anode table lines change, therefore the bond can be classified as a mixed inhibitor in acidic environments.
- The inhibition efficiency increases with increasing inhibitor concentration, reaching 90.4% at a concentration of 10⁻³ M.
- We observe good agreement between the inhibition efficiency values calculated by impedance

analysis and those obtained from the polarization curves.

- Taken together, these results confirm the effectiveness of the tested bond in inhibition and allow us to conclude that this compound is highly effective.

- The results clearly indicate the adsorption of this compound and its high protective properties on the surface of 316L stainless steel manufactured by (WAAM – CMT).

- The adsorption process can be explained by the presence of free electron pairs on the two nitrogen atoms in the inhibitor, which can form bonds with the Fe²⁺ metallic sites. In this part will be emphasize the contributions of the paper and the future applications in the research field.

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